

The cage (see figure) consists of a wooden frame 45 cm wide × 52 cm high covered with nylon screen. The cage bottom is wood. Common air conditioner foam rubber filter is stapled on intercage wood surfaces.

The preferred oviposition substrate of wax paper strips (15.24 cm wide × 60.96 cm long) are held in place vertically by slipping the paper through slots in wooden slats at the top and bottom of the cage and securing with tape. Slots are partitioned 12.5 cm apart.

C. suppressalis and *C. polychrysus* pupae in petri dishes were placed in the cage. Female adults that emerged within the cage were observed to oviposit only on the wax paper. *T. incertulas* moths collected around light sources laid 80% of their egg masses on the wax paper.

An improved oviposition cage for rice stem borers, developed at IRRI.

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Varietal reaction to rice gall midge

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Field resistance to rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* was assessed during 1981 kharif on prerelease cultivars and recommended varieties at Aduthurai. Test varieties were grown in 20-m² plots replicated 3 times. Recommended agro-nomic practices were followed except no insect control was used.

Gall midge damage was assessed 60 days after planting as the number of silver shoots among total tillers in 10 hills selected at random from each plot. Rating was by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Of the entries tested only IET3231 had no damage. Five entries recorded less than 5% damage (see table).

Gall midge damage at Tamil Nadu, India, 1981 kharif.

Variety	Parentage	Duration (days)	Damage (%)	Rating
IET3231	IR8/Siam 29	135	0.0	0
IET6010	IR8/W1263	127	0.5	1
IET6290	Leaung/IR8	135	0.8	1
IET6282	Leaung/IR8	130	4.4	3
IET6074	Vijaya/Ptb 21	130	2.3	3
IET5975	OR 10-135/W1263	130	5.0	3
IR20	IR262/TKM6	135	9.1	5
Jaya	TN1/T141	125	9.8	5
Jagannath	Mutant of T141	150	18.0	7
Pankaj (susceptible check)	Peta/Tongai Rotam	150	34.7	7
CD				11.66

Gall midge collections needed

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Discrepancies in reports on host ranges and other biological information on *Orseolia oryzae* in Asia and Africa indi-

cate a need for basic taxonomic research. Such research must be based on adequate collections of reared series from cultivated rice and from suspected wild grass hosts.

The materials needed include adult males and females with associated larvae, pupae, and pupal cases; data on host plant species and cultivars; type of

gall or other damage; locality and date of collection.

Specimens may be preserved by collecting into tubes of 70-80% alcohol. Movement of specimens within the tubes should be limited by inserting

small pieces of polythene film or tissue paper (*not* cotton-wool as it catches on claws and spines). Examination of representative series easily acquired from laboratory cultures will provide a check on culture identity.

Collections should be sent by air or sea mail (*not* air freight) to: K. M. Harris, Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, c/o British Museum (Natural History), Cromwell Road, London SW7 SBD, UK. ■

Yellow stem borer damage to rice varieties in the Punjab, India

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Activity of the yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), a pest of tall basmati type varieties in the

Punjab, was suppressed with the introduction of high-yielding dwarf varieties. But recently serious infestations have appeared in localized pockets, particularly in Ferozepur district.

Five promising rice varieties were grown in 500 m² plots at different sites as farmers' field trials. PR106 and PR107 are high-yielding dwarf varieties; IET4141 is resistant to bacterial leaf

blight and sheath rot; Basmati 370 is a traditional tall, scented variety, and Bauni Basmati is a fine-grained, scented dwarf variety.

Incidence of deadhearts and whiteheads from 20 random hills was recorded 60-70 days after transplanting and 10-15 days before harvest. Damage to Basmati 370 was most severe (see table). ■

Incidence of yellow stem borer on rice varieties at different sites in the Punjab, India, 1981 kharif.^a

Variety	Cross	Duration (days)	Deadhearts (%)					Whiteheads (%)				
			Sodhi Nagar	Hamad	Bajeke	Mamdot	Av	Sodhi Nagar	Hamad	Bajeke	Jhoke Harihar	Av
Basmati 370	Pure line selection	145-155	32.4	15.2	NP	16.0	21.2	9.6	46.0	NP	NP	27.8
Bauni Basmati	Sona/Basmati 370	145-155	28.0	9.5	NP	9.1	15.7	5.8	32.4	NP	NP	19.0
IET4141	IR8/BJI//IR22	145-155	28.0	NP	1.24	NP	14.0	8.7	NP	10.6	7.4	8.9
PR107	Jaya/Palman 579	140-145	4.9	1.1	0.67	1.3	2.0	1.9	16.8	3.2	1.1	5.8
PR106	IR8//Peta ⁵ /Belle Patna	140-145	1.7	0.3	0.00	0.7	0.7	2.9	3.8	9.3	4.0	6.1

^a NP = variety not planted at the site.

Resistance of IR varieties to insect pests

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Rice varieties IR5 to IR54 were evaluated for resistance to hoppers, leaf-folder, and caseworm in greenhouse tests; striped and yellow stem borer in

the screenhouse; and whorl maggot in the field. Damage ratings were based on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

All IR varieties except IR22 showed resistance to at least one insect (see table). Although none of the varieties are resistant to the zigzag leafhopper and leaf folder, resistant donors have been identified and are being utilized in breeding programs. ■

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Resistance of IR varieties to insect pests,^a IRRI, 1981.

Variety	Brown planthopper			Green leaf hopper	White backed plant-hopper	Zigzag leaf-hopper	Yellow stem borer	Striped stem borer	Leaf-folder	Case-worm	Whorl maggot
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3								
IR5	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR8	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR20	S	S	S	MR ^d	S	S	MR	R	S	S	S
IR22	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR24	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR26	R	S	R	MR	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR28	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR29	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR30	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR32	R	R	MR ^c	MR	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S

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